

Evaluating YOLOV5, YOLOV6, YOLOV7, and YOLOV8 in Underwater Environment: How Much Is Real Improvement?

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Abstract—This paper compares several new implementations of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection algorithms in harsh underwater environments. Using a dataset collected by a remotely operated vehicle (ROV), we evaluated the performance of YOLOv5, YOLOv6, YOLOv7, and YOLOv8 in detecting objects in challenging underwater conditions. We aimed to determine whether newer YOLO versions are superior to older ones and how much, in terms of object detection performance, for our underwater pipeline dataset. According to our findings, YOLOv5 achieved the highest mean Average Precision (mAP) score, followed by YOLOv7 and YOLOv6. When examining the precision-recall curves, YOLOv5 and YOLOv7 displayed the highest precision and recall values, respectively. Our comparison of the obtained results to those of our previous work using YOLOv4 demonstrates that each version of YOLO detectors provides significant improvement.

Index Terms—object detection, yolov5, yolov6, yolo7, yolov8, comparison

I. INTRODUCTION

Object detection is a crucial task in numerous fields, including marine biology [1], robotics [2], traffic [3], and security [4]. Detecting objects in harsh underwater environments, such as limited visibility, turbidity, and complex illumination conditions, remains a difficult problem. In recent years, object detection algorithms based on artificial intelligence have demonstrated remarkable performance in various visual recognition tasks, including object detection. The You Only Look Once (YOLO) family of deep learning object detectors gained significant attention due to its high accuracy and fast processing speed [5].

This paper is a follow-up to our previous research in [6] focussed to deep-learning approaches for object detection in images of underwater pipelines. In our previous paper, we utilized the YOLO algorithm for object detection in challenging underwater environments and demonstrated promising results on a custom dataset of underwater pipeline images. In this paper, we intend to build upon our previous research by utilizing the most recent versions of the YOLO algorithm, including YOLOv5 [7], YOLOv6 [8], YOLOv7 [9], and the latest

YOLOv8 version [10], to evaluate the algorithm’s evolution and performance in detecting objects in difficult underwater environments. By comparing the results of each version, we expect to determine the actual progress of detectors and define its most effective version in detecting objects in challenging underwater environments for our dataset.

In general, each version of YOLO has improved over its predecessor in terms of accuracy and speed. However, the extent of improvement may vary depending on the specific evaluation metric and the dataset used for testing. In order to qualitatively monitor the level of detector improvement, we will focus on Mean Average Precision (mAP) metric since it is widely used to evaluate object detection performance in computer vision [11].

Although processing speed is essential, it can vary depending on the running architecture. There is already a published comprehensive review [12] that shows improvements in mAP metrics obtained from each YOLO version. The results indicate that the detection score of YOLOv5 outperforms YOLOv4 for the mAP metric. However, the newer YOLOv6 and YOLOv8 do not outperform YOLOv5 in terms of detection score, but YOLOv7 does. Considering those findings, we aim to determine how much the harsh underwater environment affects object detection results and whether the results from the COCO dataset will correspond to those obtained on our custom dataset.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. We continue by describing the five YOLO algorithms and their main characteristics, followed by a discussion of the training dataset for the detector and training parameters. Finally, we discuss the implications of our findings and suggest future research directions in object detection in challenging underwater environments.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. YOLO versions

The YOLO algorithm has undergone significant improvements over the years, resulting in multiple versions with

improved efficiency. The 2020 release of YOLOv4 includes a spatial pyramid pooling module that enables the network to extract features at multiple scales, which improves its ability to detect objects of different sizes. In addition, YOLOv4 utilizes a new activation function known as mish, which has been demonstrated to outperform traditional activation functions such as ReLU. It uses a novel loss function that improves the training process by emphasizing challenging examples.

The YOLOv5, introduced in the same year, takes a different approach to object detection called Scaled-YOLOv4 [7]. This approach involves using anchor boxes of different scales, allowing the network to detect objects of different sizes more accurately. It also introduces the concept of image pyramids, which improves the detection of small objects in large images.

The YOLOv6 is a more recent version, introduced in 2021, built on the success of YOLOv5 by introducing new features such as anchor-free object detection [8], which eliminates the need for anchor boxes, and new classification [15] and regression [16] losses to prevent overfitting during training. It uses a new backbone based on RepVGG called EfficientRep that uses higher parallelism than previous YOLO backbones. For the neck, they Use PAN enhanced with RepBlocks or CSPStackRep. Label assignment is different due to using the Task alignment learning approach introduced in [14]. Also, the self-distillation strategy of training on its own predictions is used for the regression and classification tasks in order to achieve improved accuracy with less computational power and memory.

The YOLOv7 was proposed by the original creators of YOLOv4 in 2022 [9]. At the time, it surpassed all known object detectors in speed and accuracy in the range of 5 FPS to 160 FPS. Like YOLOv4, it was trained using only the MS COCO dataset without pre-trained backbones. YOLOv7 proposed a couple of architecture changes and a series of bag-of-freebies, which increased the accuracy without affecting the inference speed, only the training time. It uses an extended efficient layer aggregation network (E-ELAN) to allow deep learning models to learn and converge more efficiently by controlling the shortest longest gradient. Model scaling for the concatenation-based model is introduced to decrease the hardware usage of the model. The bag of freebies included planned re-parameterized convolution (like in YOLOv6), coarse label assignment for the auxiliary head and fine label assignment for the lead head, batch normalization in conv-bn-activation, implicit knowledge introduced in [13], and exponential moving average as the final inference model.

YOLOv8 was introduced in January 2023 by Ultralytics, the same company that created YOLOv5 [10]. YOLOv8 is anchor-free, reducing the number of box predictions and accelerating the Non-maximum impression (NMS). In addition, YOLOv8 uses mosaic augmentation during training; however, because it has been determined that using this augmentation throughout the entire training process is counterproductive, it is disabled for the final ten epochs.

Each of these YOLO versions has different strengths and limitations, making them suitable for different applications and

TABLE I
DATASET DESCRIPTION

Dataset	Description
Annotated images	3021
Number of Classes	5
Training	2415
Validation	303
Testing	303

environments. In this paper, we compare the performance of these five versions of YOLO in underwater pipeline object detection, with the aim of determining which version is best suited for our dataset and challenging underwater environment.

B. Data

In this research, we made use of data collected by a remotely operated vehicle (ROV) performing an underwater pipeline inspection (the dataset was first introduced in [6]). Using this dataset, we evaluated the object detection performance of various YOLO versions under conditions relevant to real-world application scenarios.

The dataset distribution is shown in Table I.

The dataset was split up into 80:10:10 ratio; the training part of the dataset consisted of 2415 different images. The testing and validation part comprised 303 images taken from three camera angles. The dataset is composed of five detection object targets: pipeline, leakage point, concrete weight, concrete mat, and pipe coupling. Each part of the dataset contains the same number of different camera angle images.

An annotation of each image is given in the text file. Images were labeled in YOLO format containing details on object class, bounding box coordinates, and the height and width of the bounding box (with the bottom-left point as the origin).

C. Training settings

To achieve optimal object detection results, it is important to choose the optimal training parameters for each version of YOLO. The number of training iterations, the learning rate, and the batch size are among the most important training parameters. The learning rate determines how quickly the network learns from the training data, with a higher learning rate potentially causing instability or overshooting the optimal solution. The batch size determines how many images are processed simultaneously during each training iteration, with larger batch sizes generally resulting in faster training but potentially resulting in memory constraints or slower convergence. The number of training iterations determines the number of times the network is exposed to the training data during training, with more iterations generally resulting in improved performance but possibly causing overfitting or longer training times. In addition to these parameters, each YOLO version may have its own optimal training parameters.

In this paper, we carefully selected the training parameters presented in Table II for each YOLO version to ensure the best performance. The same parameters were used for the YOLOv5, YOLOv7, and YOLOv8 object detectors, while for

TABLE II
TRAINING PARAMETERS CONFIGURATION

Model	Learning rate	Batch	Decay	Momentum
YOLOv5l6	0.01	64	0.0005	0.937
YOLOv6l6	0.0032	64	0.00036	0.843
YOLOv7-e6e	0.01	64	0.0005	0.937
YOLOv8x	0.01	64	0.0005	0.937

YOLOv6, we used the parameters proposed by the author. For each version of the YOLO detector, we used the pre-trained models with the highest number of parameters available on GitHub repositories and then fine-tuned each model using the custom dataset. Although we compare five different results for object detectors, this table does not show parameters for YOLOv4; those parameters can be found in the previous paper [6].

III. RESULTS

In this section, we present underwater pipeline object detection results for different versions of YOLO models. We trained each version on the same custom dataset and tested the resulting models on the test part of the dataset to measure their performance. First, we will present loss charts; Fig. 1 shows the loss function for YOLOv4, YOLOv5, and YOLOv7. We included YOLOv4 loss from previous work [6] and only two of four tested models in this work, YOLOv5, and YOLOv7, since those models show minimum loss results.

The object detection results obtained by the trained models on our custom underwater pipeline image dataset are as follows. In general, excellent results had been achieved for all YOLO detectors, but more importantly, we can see from Table III that newer YOLO versions performed better than the reference result obtained from YOLOv4. The mAP is an often-used metric that calculates the average precision for each class across varied Intersection over Union (IoU). In this study, the threshold was set to 0.5, and it was shown that the YOLOv5 delivered the best mAP result of 97.10% on the test dataset. YOLOv7 was close, with an mAP metric of 96.30%, followed by YOLOv6 with an mAP of 95.30%. YOLOv8 achieved an mAP of 95.10%, while the oldest version of the YOLO detector used in this study, YOLOv4, had the lowest mAP at 94.21%. These results suggest that YOLOv5 and YOLOv7 were the most effective versions of the YOLO algorithm for detecting objects in underwater conditions on our dataset, with YOLOv6 and YOLOv8 also showing excellent performance.

However, it is worth noting that the difference in the mAP metric between the versions was relatively small, indicating that all versions of the YOLO algorithm are capable of achieving high levels of object detection accuracy in this challenging environment.

Second, to further compare the performance of the two best YOLO detectors, we plotted the precision-recall (PR) curves for YOLOv5 and YOLOv7. The PR curves show the trade-off between precision and recall for different detection thresholds. As shown in Fig. 2, both YOLOv5 and YOLOv7 achieved high

Fig. 1. (a) Loss function and mAP result for reference model YOLOv4 [6], (b) Loss function for YOLOv5, (c) Loss function for YOLOv7.

TABLE III
TABLE TYPE STYLES

Architecture	Precision	Recall	mAP(%)
YOLOv4	0.901	0.951	94.21
YOLOv5	0.901	0.951	97.10
YOLOv6	0.778	0.857	95.30
YOLOv7	0.885	0.955	96.30
YOLOv8	0.84	0.969	95.10

precision and recall across a range of detection thresholds, with YOLOv5 having slightly higher recall values for three target classes.

And last result comparison of our four utilized object detection is the confidence level. We analyzed the confidence levels of the detected objects using the F1 confidence curve. This curve shows the relationship between the F1 score and the detection confidence threshold, which is the minimum confidence level required for a detection to be considered positive.

Fig. 3 shows the F1 confidence curves for YOLOv5 and YOLOv7, which achieved the highest F1 scores in our test

Fig. 2. (a) Precision-recall curve for YOLOv7, (b) Precision-recall curve for YOLOv7.

dataset. Both detectors show a similar trend, with the highest F1 score achieved at a confidence threshold of around 0.6. At lower confidence thresholds, the F1 score decreases due to an increasing number of false positives, while at higher confidence thresholds, the F1 score decreases due to an increasing number of false negatives.

These F1 confidence curves provide additional information about the trade-off between precision and recall and can be used to adjust the confidence threshold of the detector for specific applications. Overall, our results show that YOLOv7 and YOLOv5 are the most accurate detectors for object detection in harsh underwater conditions, and the F1 confidence curves can be used to optimize their performance for specific detection tasks.

Fig. 3. (a) F1 confidence curve for YOLOv7, (b) F1 confidence curve for YOLOv5.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have evaluated the performance of four variants of the YOLO algorithm for the detection of objects in underwater environments. In terms of the mAP metric, YOLOv5 achieved the highest overall detection accuracy, followed by YOLOv7, YOLOv6, and YOLOv8. In order to demonstrate and validate the actual state of development of the YOLO detectors, we compared our results to those from previous work that utilized YOLOv4. Interestingly, although newer versions claim better performance, we discovered that the older YOLOv5 model performed better than the newer YOLOv6, YOLOv7, and YOLOv8 models on our dataset.

In terms of future work, the performance of YOLO in harsh underwater environments has the potential for improvement. One area of emphasis could be the collection of more diverse and extensive datasets for training the models, which could lead to improved detection precision. In addition, investigating additional object detection algorithms and comparing them to YOLO could provide valuable insight into the optimal approach for this particular use case.

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